

THE ROLE OF INSTAGRAM ACCOUNT @myquranbest IN MOTIVATING FOLLOWERS' WORSHIP ACTIVITIES

ANDY MAKHRIAN ¹, Madya Dr. CHE HASNIZA BINTI CHE NOH ² and

Dr. NURUL HIDAYAH BINTI MAT ³

^{1,3} Centre for Fundamental and Continuing Education, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu.

Email: ¹andy.unib@gmail.com, ³hidayah.mat@umt.edu.my

² Professor, Centre for Fundamental and Continuing Education, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu.

Email: niza@umt.edu.my

Abstract

Social media is one of the new types of media. One of the most widely used types of social media today is Instagram, in Indonesia according to a survey conducted by Hotsuite (we are social), Instagram is the second most used social media by people after WhatsApp. In this day and age, many things have changed, one of which is the way people get information, Instagram itself is a place that is widely used by a person or group to spread information, one of which is religious information. @myquranbest Instagram account is an Instagram account belonging to a group that consistently spreads Islamic da'wah through Instagram, one of which is about worship. This study aims to find out whether Instagram accounts @myquranbest affect followers' worship activities. This survey-based quantitative study uses a quantitative methodology. In this study, the questionnaire and literature review methods were used to collect data in the form of additional books, journals, and previous related research. The population of this study consisted of followers of @myquranbest Instagram accounts, and the sample consisted of 91 respondents. The data analysis method used in this study is linear regression using SPSS 26 software. The results of this study show that there is an influence of @myquranbest Instagram Accounts on Worship Activities on Followers. In this study, it was found that arithmetic t is greater than t table so that there is an influence of Variable X (Instagram account @myquranbest) on Variable Y (worship activities).

Keywords: Instagram, @myquranbest Accounts, Worship Activities, Followers.

1. BACKGROUND

Along with the passage of time, the advancement of communication and information technology is also accelerating. In addition, several sectors are changing, such as technology, information, and communication are growing rapidly, and the development of some of these sectors has given rise to new media. The emergence of new media based on advances in internet technology has had a significant impact on people around the world. Social media is a new type of media. It is an internet medium that allows its users to represent themselves or interact, cooperate, share, and communicate with other users to form virtual social bonds [1].

The development of digital technology has changed the landscape of social interaction and information dissemination, including in religious contexts. Social media, especially Instagram, has become a significant platform in spreading Islamic content and influencing the religious practices of its users [2] This phenomenon reflects a shift in the way religious people access and interact with their religious teachings, which ([3] refers to as 'digital religion'. According to a Hootsuite survey, internet users in Indonesia amounted to 204.7 million people (73.7 percent of the total population of 277.7 million people) and active social media users in

Indonesia amounted to 191.4 million people, an increase from the previous year [4].

Furthermore, this phenomenon also raises questions about religious authority in the digital era. As revealed [5] social media has created a new space for the emergence of "alternative religious authorities" that can influence religious interpretation and practice. In this case, @myquranbest can be seen as one of the new forms of religious authority that have emerged on digital platforms. In addition, other data also states that data from [6] shows that 73.7% of Indonesia's population is active users of social media, with Instagram being one of the most popular platforms. Of these, 62% of users admitted to using social media to find information, including religious information. This phenomenon shows the great potential of accounts such as @myquranbest in influencing the religious views and practices of their users.

On the other hand, the ease of access to religious content through social media also poses new challenges. Users are faced with a variety of religious interpretations and views that can sometimes lead to confusion or even conflict. Therefore, digital and religious literacy skills are becoming increasingly important for users in filtering and understanding the information they receive [7]. Instagram is one of the many social media platforms available today. In addition, Instagram is one of the most popular social media platforms among Indonesia, according to the findings of a survey conducted by Hootsuite (We are Social) in February 2024, which found that Instagram is second only to Whatsapp as the most popular social media platform in Indonesia.

One of the Instagram accounts that stands out in the spread of Islamic content is @myquranbest. With the number of followers reaching more than 500 thousand (as of August 2024), this account has become a source of inspiration and religious knowledge for many Instagram users in Indonesia. The content shared by @myquranbest, ranging from Quranic verse quotes, hadiths, to religious advice, has the potential to affect the understanding and worship practices of its followers. In the midst of the rapid development of the current era, it is inevitable that people's mindset will change; Generally, people are more interested in instant things, and this is reflected in their need for information. Not even in the realm of da'wah, according to [8], da'wah is an effort to invite people to The right way to fit with God's commands for the good or salvation of the world. Currently, many people use social media as a platform for da'wah, and many people are starting to use social media as a forum for information and education to display da'wah activities.

To practice Islam, religious activities in the form of worship are needed. Individuals engage in worship activities in the form of words and deeds, both openly and secretly, to achieve God's blessings. @myquranbest Instagram account is the official Instagram account for the Quran Digital Quran Best application. @myquranbest Instagram account was created for the main purpose of spreading Shia Islam, which is a target, especially among the demographics of the most popular social media users in Indonesia, the millennial generation. This study seeks to find out whether Instagram accounts @myquranbest affect the worship activities of their followers.

By understanding the dynamics between digital da'wah, users, and religious practices, this study is expected to provide valuable insights into how social media technology is shaping the contemporary religious landscape in Indonesia. Furthermore, this understanding can help in the development of more effective and relevant da'wah strategies in the digital era, as well as encourage the wiser use of social media in religious contexts. This study aims to find out whether Instagram accounts @myquranbest affect followers' worship activities. In this context, we will investigate how the content shared by the account can affect the motivation, understanding, and daily worship practices of its followers. This study is important considering the growing role of social media in shaping people's perceptions and behaviors, especially in religious matters.

Theoretical Foundations

@myquranbest Instagram Account

The @Myqurabest Instagram account is the official account for the best digital app of the Qur'an. @myquranbest Instagram account was created for the main purpose of evangelizing shia islam, which is a target, especially among millennials, who are the largest social media user base in Indonesia. This account was established in 2019 in bandung, west java. @myquranbest Instagram account is an account that is always consistent in displaying its content. They upload content every day in the form of Instagram pictures and video reels.

Another definition states that @myquranbest is an Instagram account that focuses on spreading Islamic content, especially related to the Quran. This account shares various types of content such as Quranic verse quotes, translations, tafsirs, hadiths, and religious advice packaged in an attractive and easy-to-understand visual form. The main purpose of this account is to inspire and educate its followers about the teachings of Islam through social media platforms (www.quranbest.com).

Research related to the influence of religious Instagram accounts on the worship behavior of its followers has shown some interesting findings. In a study conducted by [9] it was found that 78% of respondents reported an increase in the frequency of worship after following da'wah accounts on Instagram, 65% felt more motivated to learn the Quran after being exposed to content from these accounts and 82% felt their understanding of Islamic teachings improved thanks to the posts they saw on Instagram.

Meanwhile [10] in his research on the impact of Islamic content on social media on the millennial generation, found that visual content such as infographics and pictorial quotes tended to be more effective in attracting attention and increasing the retention of religious information, Active interaction with content, such as giving likes and comments, was positively correlated with the increase in daily religious practices.

Worship Activities

Activity refers to a series of actions or processes carried out by a person or group of people to achieve a specific goal. Activities can be physical, mental, social, or a combination of all of them. In a broader context, activities can also include work, recreation, or daily activities that

are carried out on a regular basis. Activities are usually related to the effort or energy expended to do something productive or meaningful [11].

Worship activities are a series of actions or rituals carried out by individuals or groups as a form of devotion and respect to God or other spiritual forces. These activities include various religious practices such as prayer, fasting, reading the holy book, dhikr, and other actions aimed at getting closer to God. Worship activities are not only limited to formal rituals, but also include daily behaviors carried out with the intention of worship, such as helping others or maintaining the cleanliness of the environment [12]

Humans are involved in various activities in their daily lives. According to [13], activity is not just an activity; rather, it is seen as an effort to achieve a goal or meet a need. Whether an activity has significance or not depends on the individual. From the previous definition, it can be concluded that activity is an activity, a busy state, or can be interpreted as cooperation carried out by each individual or group in an effort to be better than before.

The worship of a servant to his God consists of humbling himself as much as possible, with a sincere heart, in accordance with the way determined by religion [14] Thus, Ibadah in Islam refers to all forms of devotion, obedience, and respect performed by a Muslim to Allah SWT. Worship includes all actions, both ritual (such as prayer, fasting, zakat, hajj) and daily deeds that are carried out with the intention of obtaining Allah's pleasure. In Islam, worship is not only limited to formal religious activities, but also includes every good action carried out in daily life, as long as it is based on the right intention and in accordance with the sharia [15]

In his lecture [16], Hasbi Al Shiddieqy revealed the terminology of worship which was described, according to the scholars of Tawhid, worship is the advice of Allah and His glorification with all His obedience and humility to Him, According to the morals of worship of the scholars, all physical obedience to Allah is practiced by upholding His Sharia, According to the Sufi scholars, worship is an act of mukalaf that is contrary to his lust to glorify his Lord, Worship, according to the jurisprudence of the scholars, is all obedience done to obtain Allah's favor by expecting His reward in the hereafter and Worship, according to Jumbuh scholars, is a term that covers everything that Allah enjoys and loves in the form of words and deeds, both light and silent.

The knowledge of worship gained must be applied in daily life. All his actions must be guided by his religious understanding. To practice Islam, it is necessary to carry out religious activities in the form of worship. Worship activities are busy work related to worship issues, meaning that the busy activity or work is in the form of actions intended to get God's blessings. Based on various definitions of worship, the construction of Worship Activities in this study is all activities carried out by individuals to obtain Allah's blessings in the form of words and deeds, either openly or secretly. This study also considers the views of [17] about various types of worship. As a result, worship is divided into two types in this study: Khassah (Special) worship which has definite provisions in every work, and Ammah (General) worship which includes all deeds that bring goodness and are done with sincere intentions for Allah.

According to [17] in their book *Menyelami seluk-beluk ibadah dalam Islam*, worship can be broadly classified into two types:

1. *Khassah* (special) worship or *mahdhah* worship (worship with certain conditions), which is worship whose provisions and implementation have been determined by *nash* and which is the essence of worship to Allah Ta'al. Prayer, fasting, zakat, and hajj are examples.
2. Worshipping '*ammah* (general), that is, all good deeds done with sincere intentions in the name of Allah Ta'alsa. Such as drinking, eating, and earning a living.

The arrangement of man's relationship with God has been designed in such a way that it cannot change over time.

Stimulus-Organism-Response Theory

The SOR theory model is used in this study (Stimulus, Organism, Response). The SOR theory first emerged in the 1930s. It is a classic communication model that is heavily influenced by psychological theory. The acronym SOR stands for Stimulus, Organism, and Response. The basic assumption of this theory is that the mass media has a direct, direct, and direct effect on communicators. SR Theory stands for Stimulus Response Theory. This model shows that communication is a two-way street. The model assumes that certain verbal words, nonverbal gestures, and symbols will elicit a specific response from others [18].

According to this theory, any behavior is essentially a response or response to a Stimulus. Stimulus is an event that occurs both outside and inside the human body and causes a change in behavior. The presence of a stimulus causes a change in behavior, which is accompanied by a response. The following are the components of the research: Da'wah content is posted on @myquranbest Instagram accounts as a message/stimulus. In this study, communicators/organizations are followers or followers of @myquranbest Instagram accounts. The effect/response is an increase in worship activities among followers or followers of @myquranbest Instagram account.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach. The type of research used in this study is survey research. According to [19] survey research is a type of approach that involves sampling (random or representative) of the population to be studied and asking one or more questions about attitudes, perceptions, or behaviors to survey subjects. The sampling technique used in this study is Probability Sampling with a simple random sampling technique, with the population considered homogeneous so that the entire population has the same chance as the sample in the study. According to Fowler in [19], the samples selected in a research approach with a survey method must accurately describe or represent the population being studied. The researchers used the Taro Yamane formula with a pressure of 10% to determine the number of samples in this study, and after calculating the sample using the Taro Yamane formula, the number of respondents in this study was obtained as many as 91 respondents [20].

The Guttman scale was used in this study. In this study, the data was analyzed using quantitative techniques and simple linear regression formulas. The hypothesis was tested after analysis using a simple linear regression formula. The goal is to determine whether the proposed hypothesis is accepted or rejected. If the null hypothesis test (H0) is rejected, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted, and vice versa. The T test method was used to test the hypothesis in this study. The T-test is used to determine how far individual variable X (partially) affects the variable Y in a study. The t-test compares the t-count value with the t-table value on the condition that if the t-count > t-table, then there is an influence of the X variable (Instagram account @myquranbest) on the Y variable (worship activities in followers), which means that the working hypothesis (Ha) is accepted and the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected [21].

Research Chart

Figure 1: Research Frameworks

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of Instagram Account @myquranbest on Worship Activities on Followers. The primary data of this study was obtained by distributing a questionnaire to followers of @myquranbest Instagram account, with a total sample size of 91 respondents. The sampling technique used in this study is Probability Sampling, which is a sampling technique that provides an equal opportunity for each element/member of the population to be selected as a sample member and homogeneous with a simple random sampling type.

Characteristics Responden

A total of 91 respondents who were followers of Instagram accounts @myquranbest participated in this study. To determine specifically the respondents who filled out the questionnaire, the researchers determined the characteristics of the respondents in this study, which included gender, age, profession, and education level.

Table 1: Respondent's Gender

No.	Gender	Total
1.	Male	21 Respondents
2.	Female	70 Respondents

Source: Researcher, 2024

According to Table 1, 70 of the total 91 respondents in this study were women, while the remaining 21 were men.

Table 2: Respondent's Age

No.	Age	Total
1.	18 years	1 Respondent
2.	19 years	3 Respondent
3.	20 years	5 Respondent
4.	21 years	28 Respondent
5.	22 years	31 Respondent
6.	23 years	14 Respondent
7.	24 years	3 Respondent
8.	25 years	2 Respondent
9.	26 years	2 Respondent
10.	27 years	2 Respondent

Source: Researcher, 2024

The majority of those who follow the Instagram account @myquranbest 22 years old (31 respondents), while those who follow the least account are 18 years old.

Table 3: Respondent's Profession

No.	Profession	Total
1.	Student	68 Respondent
2.	Private employees	12 Respondent
3.	Self-employed	4 Respondent
4.	State Civil Apparatus/ASN	3 Respondent
5.	Nurse	1 Respondent
6.	Fresh Graduate	2 Respondent
7.	Freelance	1 Respondent

Source: Researcher, 2024

The number of students recorded 68 out of the total respondents in this study were students, and the respondents with the lowest jobs were nurses and freelance day workers, each with one respondent.

Table 4: Respondent's Education

No.	Education	Total
1.	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	21 Responden
2.	D III	6 Responden
3.	Professional Education/Nurse	1 Responden
4.	S1	61 Responden
5.	S2	2 Responden

Source: Researcher, 2024

The least common type of education among the respondents in this study was professional/nursing education, with a total of 1 respondent, while the most common type of education was the list of the most education, or S1.

Table 5: Simple Linear Regression Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	5.452	1.093		4.990	.000
@myquranbest Instagram Account	.424	.120	.351	3.533	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Worship Activities

Source: SPSS 26 Results, 2024

From table 5 above, the elaboration of the results states that the Interpretation of Constant Coefficient B = 5.452: This is the base value of the dependent variable (e.g., followers' worship activities) when the value of the independent variable (Instagram account @myquranbest) is zero. In other words, it shows the estimated worship activities that are predicted when there is no influence from @myquranbest Instagram account.

Coefficient @myquranbest

B = 0.424: Each unit increase in exposure or influence from @myquranbest Instagram account is expected to increase followers' worship activities by 0.424 units. This positive coefficient shows a direct and positive relationship between the existence or activity of @myquranbest Instagram account and the level of worship activities of its followers.

The Model Quality Evaluation states that the Standard Error is that Constant: 1.093 and Instagram Account @myquranbest: 0.120. Small error standards indicate more accurate estimates for these coefficients. This is important because it provides confidence in the accuracy of the model's predictions.

Normalized Coefficient (Beta) with the explanation that Beta = 0.351: This indicates the strength of the influence of the Instagram account @myquranbest relative to the dependent variable. A positive and not too large beta shows a significant influence but is not too dominant. The Significance Test states that t-Statistic and p-value, $t = 3.533$ and p-value (p-value is incomplete but estimated ≤ 0.01): A high t-value and a very small p-value indicate that the coefficient for @myquranbest Instagram account is statistically significant. This means that there is strong evidence that this independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable, and this effect does not occur by chance. R-Square (determination coefficient): Although the R-Square value is not given, it is important to assess how well this model explains the variation in the dependent variable. R-Square measures the proportion of variability in the dependent variables described by the regression model.

There is an influence of @myquranbest Instagram Accounts on Worship Activities on Followers, especially with a significance value less than the significance level of 0.1, according to the results of the table of data analysis results above, which uses a simple linear regression in this study. This conclusion is further supported by the findings of the research hypothesis test, which uses the t test by comparing the t count and the t table and whose results state that there is a Regarding the influence of @myquranbest Instagram accounts on worship activities on followers, this statistic is positive and stands at 0.424, indicating that for every 1% increase in following Instagram accounts @myquranbest, Worship activities for followers increased by 0.424.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.351 ^a	.123	.113	1.234

a. Predictors: (Constant), @myquranbest Instagram Account
Source : SPSS 26 Results, 2024

The Summary Model form shown in the table above is the result of the value of the determination coefficient (R Square), which shows the magnitude of the influence of variable X on variable Y of 12.3%. And the remaining 87.7% are influenced by factors other than the variables that have been tested. Instagram accounts like @myquranbest have an impact on the worship activities of their followers. @myquranbest Instagram account is a da'wah account

that aims to spread Shia da'wah through Instagram to the millennial generation, who make up the majority of Instagram users in Indonesia, through content that includes worship and learning about other religions. According to the findings of this study, the purpose of @myquranbest Instagram account is to spread Islamic da'wah and increase worship activities among its followers through the content they upload.

In order to increase worship activities among its followers, @myquranbest Instagram account must accept whatever it receives for such religious posts and be willing to accept any risks associated with worship activities among its followers. Despite the fact that it has displayed religious posts in the form of special worship recommendations and general worship to followers, it will still allow followers to express doubts or disbelief about what has been displayed.

Thus, the results of this study are directly proportional to the theory used by the researchers in this study, namely Stimulus Organism Response (SOR), which states that behavioral changes will occur if the stimulus given to the organism causes the organism to respond. The stimulus in this study is the religious da'wah message uploaded or shared by @myquranbest Instagram account to their followers. This was done to attract the attention of followers so that the message conveyed could be received by the followers of the @myquranbest Instagram account, and finally a response from followers appeared in the form of an increase in worship activities after following and seeing the religious uploads displayed by the @myquranbest Instagram account.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn: it was found that the significance value of the @myquranbest Instagram Account (Variable X) of 0.001 was less than the significance value determined in this study, which was 10% or 0.1, indicating that there was an Influence of @myquranbest Instagram Accounts on Worship Activities on Followers. The results of the t-test calculation also revealed that the t-count was greater than the t-table ($3,536 > 1,662$), implying that H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected in this study. Then, according to the results of the coefficient of determination (R Square) that can be found in the study, the influence exerted by Variable X on Variable Y is 12.3% and can be classified as small because the remaining 87.7% is influenced by factors outside the scope of the study.

According to the findings of the research questionnaire, Instagram account followers @myquranbest not only become conscious, but also change their behavior, such as increasing their worship. The increase in worship activities for followers is in the form of carrying out worship activities that were not previously carried out, becoming aware of the correct worship procedures and applying/evaluating worship, and there is an increase in worship. Instagram followers @myquranbest predominantly female, with an average follower age of 20 years old and the majority of student jobs with an average undergraduate education.

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